

NanOx4EStor

Nanoscaled ferroelectric (pseudo)-binary oxide thin film supercapacitors for flexible and ultrafast pulsed power electronics

At a Glance

Funded under: M-ERA.NET3

Overall budget: € 642.822,00

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Coordinated by: University of Minho, Portugal

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The Project

The main goal of the **NanOx4EStor** project is to develop innovative and cost effective high-throughput technologies for the fabrication of advanced supercapacitors based on wake-up free (pseudo)-binary oxide thin films, fabricated by physical vapour deposition (PVD) processes, with optimized ferroelectric and energy storage (ES) properties through (i) strain, (ii) interface and (iii) dead-layer engineering.

Consortium

University of
Minho (UMinho),
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National Institute
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Physics (NIMP),
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ÉCOLE
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École Centrale de
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Dissemination

Project website:

<https://inl.cnrs.fr/projects/nanox4estor/>

 LinkedIn Group

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9260371/>

 ResearchGate

<https://www.researchgate.net/project/Nanoscaled-ferroelectric-pseudo-binary-oxide-thin-film-supercapacitors-for-flexible-and-ultrafast-pulsed-power-electronics>

Publications

12. G. Magagnin, J. Bouaziz, M. L. Berre, S. Gonzalez, D. Deleruyelle, B. Vilquin, Comparative performance of fluorite-structured materials for nanosupercapacitor applications featured, *APL Mater.* 12, 071124 (2024).
11. T. Zakusylo, A. Quintana, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, J. L. O. Yano, J. Lyu, J. Sort, F. Sánchez, I. Fina, Robust multiferroicity and magnetic modulation of the ferroelectric imprint field in heterostructures comprising epitaxial $\text{Hf}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ and Co. *Mater. Horiz.*, 11, 2388-2396 (2024).
10. A. R. Jayakrishnan, J. S. Kim, M. Hellenbrand, L. S. Marques, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, Growth of emergent simple pseudo-binary ferroelectrics and their potential in neuromorphic computing devices. *Horiz.*, 11, 2355-2371 (2024).
9. A. R. Jayakrishnan, V. B. Isfahani, S. K. P. Nair, K. C. Sekhar, L. S. Marques, M. Pereira, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, The benefits of incorporating lead-free ferroelectric materials in high energy density Li-and Li-free batteries, *Journal of Energy Storage* 97, Part A, 112846 (2024).

Conference presentations and proceedings

32. G. Magagnin, J. Bouaziz, M. Le Berre, S. Gonzalez, E. Puyoo, D. Deleruyelle, B. Vilquin, "Hf_{1-x}Zr_xO₂ monolayers for nanosupercapacitors: a performance assessment study", XXXIX RSEF Physics Biennial, San Sebastian, Spain, 15-19 July 2024.
31. Rebecca Cervasio, Jordan Bouaziz, Marine Verseils, Pierre Hemme, Jean-Blaise Brubach, Ingrid Canero Infante, Greta Segantini, Pedro Rojo Romeo, Alessandro Coati, Alina Vlad, Andrea Resta, Yves Garreau, Claudia Decorse, Emilie Amzallag, Jerome Creuze, Pascale Roy, Bertrand Vilquin, "Deposition optimization, infrared spectroscopy and *ab initio* simulations of ferroelectric HfZrO₂ thin films" CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
30. G. Magagnin, J. Bouaziz, M. Le Berre, S. Gonzalez, D. Deleruyelle, B. Vilquin, "High energy storage antiferroelectric fluorite nanosupercapacitors" CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
29. M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, R. F. Negrea, J. P. B. Silva, "Transmission electron microscopy studies of ferroelectric ZrO₂ thin films", EMC 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark, 25-30 August 2024.
28. M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, J. P. B. Silva, "New Deposition Method For Achieving Ferroelectric Orthorhombic ZrO₂", ROCAM 2024, Bucharest, Romania, 15-18 July 2024.
27. V. Lenzi, A., J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, "Effect of oxygen vacancies in ferroelectric properties and phase stability of ZrO₂ thin films". CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
26. N. E. Silva, J. S. Kim, M. Hellenbrand, N. Strkalj, M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, T. Rebelo, B. Almeida, L. S. Marques, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, "Resistive switching in epitaxial rhombohedral HfO₂ ultra-thin films" CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
25. A. Silva, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, "Doping effect on the phase stability and ferroelectric properties in ZrO₂". CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
24. N. E. Silva, A. R. Jayakrishnan, A. Kaim, K. Gwozdz, L. Domingues, M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, M. Pereira, L. Marques, R. L. Z. Hoye, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, "Ferroelectric ZrO₂ thin films for high-performing near-infrared photodetection", CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
23. E. M. F. Vieira, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, A. L. Pires, A. M. Pereira, J.H. Correia, "Optimization of binary oxides properties for energy harvesting". CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024.
22. I. Fina, T. Song, H. Tan, T. Zakusylo, A. Quintana, N. Diz, P. Koutsogiannis, J. L. Ortola, J. Lyu, S. Estandia, C. Magén, J. A. Pardo, V. Lenzi, J. Silva, L. Marques, J. Sort, F. Sanchez. "Epitaxial ferroelectric hafnia as a suitable platform for fundamental and novel phenomena investigations". CMD31 2024, Braga, Portugal 2-6 september 2024. 22. T. Song, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, I. Fina, F. Sánchez, "Disentangling stress and strain effects in ferroelectric HfO₂". ROCAM - 10th International Conference on Advanced Materials. Bucharest, Romania 29 July 2024.
21. I. Fina, T. Song, H. Tan, T. Zakusylo, A. Quintana, N. Diz, P. Koutsogiannis, J. L. Ortola, J. Lyu, S. Estandia, C. Magén, J. A. Pardo, V. Lenzi, J. Silva, L. Marques, J. Sort, F. Sanchez. "Epitaxial ferroelectric hafnia as a suitable platform for fundamental and novel phenomena investigations". NanoTech Poland 2024. Poznan, Poland 5-7 June 2024.
20. I. Fina, T. Song, H. Tan, T. Zakusylo, A. Quintana, N. Diz, P. Koutsogiannis, J. L. Ortola, J. Lyu, S. Estandia, C. Magén, J. A. Pardo, V. Lenzi, J. Silva, L. Marques, J. Sort, F. Sanchez. "Epitaxial ferroelectric Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ films as a platform to study interface-layer engineering effects". E-MRS 2024 Spring Meeting, Strasburg, France 27-31 May 2024.
19. A. Silva, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, "Phase stability and polarization in doped ZrO₂". Novel High-k Application Workshop 2024 no NaMLab gGmbH Dresden, Germany, 11-12 March 2024.

18. J. P. B. Silva, “The promise of ferroelectric binary oxides for autonomous IoT sensors”. Seminar for the Device Materials Group from Professor Judith Driscoll, Dra. Giuliana di Martino and Prof. Sohini Kar-Narayan. University of Cambridge, United Kingdom, 24 June 2024.
17. N. E. Silva, A. R. Jayakrishnan, A. Kaim, K. Gwozdz, L. Domingues, M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, M. Pereira, L. Marques, R. L. Z. Hoye, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, “Self-powered near-infrared photodetectors based on ferroelectric ZrO₂ thin films”, XXXIX RSEF Physics Biennial, San Sebastian, Spain, 15-19 July 2024.
16. A. Quintana, T. Zakusylo, J. L. O. Yano, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, J. Lyu, J. Sort, F. Sánchez, I. Fina, “Co/Hf_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ multiferroic heterostructures”, XXXIX RSEF Physics Biennial, San Sebastian, Spain, 15-19 July 2024.
15. A. Silva, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, “Tuning of ferroelectric properties in doped ZrO₂”. XXXIX RSEF Physics Biennial, San Sebastian, Spain, 15-19 July 2024.
14. J. P. B. Silva, V. Lenzi, C. M. Istrate, C. Ghica, L. S. Marques, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll “Ferroelectric epitaxial ZrO₂ thin films”. European Conference on Applications of Polar Dielectrics (ECAPD-2024), Trondheim, Norway 16-19 June 2024.
13. N. E. Silva, A. R. Jayakrishnan, A. Kaim, K. Gwozdz, L. Domingues, M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, M. Pereira, L. Marques, R. L. Z. Hoye, J. L. MacManus-Driscoll, J. P. B. Silva, “Ferroelectric oxide thin films as an emerging candidate for self-powered photodetection”. European Conference on Applications of Polar Dielectrics (ECAPD-2024), Trondheim, Norway, 16-19 June 2024.
12. A. Silva, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, “Polarization and relative phase stability in doped ZrO₂”. European Conference on Applications of Polar Dielectrics (ECAPD-2024), Trondheim, Norway 16-19 June 2024.

Emergent ferroelectric and antiferroelectric ZrO₂ and HZO films for energy storage

Antiferroelectric ZrO₂ thin film strikes a balance between ferroelectric and linear dielectric behavior, showing reduced losses compared to the ferroelectric sample but an energy storage density as high as 52 J/cm³ at 3.5 MV/cm. This value can be further increased up to 84 J/cm³ at a higher electrical field (4.0 MV/cm), with an efficiency of 75%, among the highest values reported for fluorite-structured materials. Find out more about these very exciting results in: G. Magagnin, et al. APL Mater. 12, 071124 (2024).

Energy density storage vs cycles and (b) efficiency (η) vs cycles until breakdown for FE HZO, AFE ZrO₂, LD HZO, and LD ZrO₂ at an applied electric field of 3.5 MV/cm. For comparison, AFE ZrO₂ at 4 MV/cm is also shown.

Nanox4EStor present at CMD31 to discuss the advances in ferroelectric and antiferroelectric binary oxides

Ecole Centrale de Lyon (ECL) and University of Minho research teams, in the framework of M-ERA.NET project Nanox4EStor, participated in the mini-colloquia Emergent Ferroelectrics co-organized by Dr. José Silva at CMD31 conference, in Braga.

